

PSYCHOLOGICAL CONDITIONS AFFECTING INTERNET ADDICTION IN ADOLESCENTS

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada o‘smirlik davrida internetdan ortiqcha foydalanish va internetga qaramlik shakllanishiga ta’sir etuvchi psixik holatlar tahlil qilinadi. Internet texnologiyalarining keng tarqalishi natijasida yoshlar orasida virtual muhitga haddan tashqari berilish holatlari ko‘paymoqda. O‘smirlik davri psixologik jihatdan sezgir davr bo‘lib, ushbu bosqichda emotsional beqarorlik, o‘zini anglash jarayonlari va ijtimoiy munosabatlarga ehtiyoj kuchayadi. Shu sababli, ayrim psixologik omillar – yolg‘izlik hissi, tashvishlilik, depressiv holatlar, past o‘z-o‘zini baholash va stress – internetga qaramlikni shakllantiruvchi muhim omillar sifatida namoyon bo‘ladi. Maqolada ushbu psixik holatlarning internetdan foydalanish xulq-atvori bilan bog‘liqligi ilmiy manbalar asosida yoritiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: internetga qaramlik, o‘smirlar psixologiyasi, psixoemotsional holat, tashvishlilik, depressiya, ijtimoiy moslashuv, virtual muhit.

Abstract. This article analyzes the psychological states that influence excessive Internet use and the formation of Internet addiction in adolescence. As a result of the widespread use of Internet technologies, cases of excessive dependence on the virtual environment are increasing among young people. Adolescence is a psychologically sensitive period, during which emotional instability, self-awareness processes, and the need for social relationships increase. Therefore, some psychological factors - a sense of loneliness, anxiety, depressive states, low self-esteem, and stress - appear as important factors in the formation of Internet addiction. The article discusses the relationship of these psychological states with Internet use behavior based on scientific sources.

Keywords: Internet addiction, adolescent psychology, psychoemotional state, anxiety, depression, social adaptation, virtual environment.

Introduction. In recent years, the rapid development of information technologies has penetrated almost all areas of human life. In particular, the Internet plays an important role in the daily life of the younger generation. Although the Internet allows for learning, communication, and meaningful leisure, its excessive use can cause some psychological problems. Adolescence is one of the most complex stages of personal development. During this period, a person's self-awareness increases, the need for social relationships increases, and emotional stability is not sufficiently formed. Therefore, adolescents quickly adapt to the virtual environment, and in some cases, Internet addiction may occur.

The concept of Internet addiction has been actively studied in psychology since the end of the 20th century. This condition is characterized by a person's inability to control their use of the Internet and the occurrence of unpleasant psychological states when they are away from it [1].

Studies show that Internet addiction often develops in connection with certain psychological states - depression, anxiety, social isolation, and low self-esteem [2].

Literature review. The problem of Internet addiction has been studied by a number of foreign and domestic researchers. American psychologist K. Young defines Internet addiction as a psychological dependence and interprets it as a phenomenon associated with impaired impulse control [3]. According to his research, excessive use of the Internet has a negative impact on the real social life of a person. M. Griffiths also considers Internet addiction to be one of the forms of behavioral addiction and includes its main symptoms as a desire for psychological satisfaction, loss of time control, and restriction of real-life activities [4, 12]. Studies show that the psychoemotional state of adolescents plays an important role in the development of Internet addiction. For example, adolescents who experience high levels of anxiety or stress may perceive the virtual environment as a means of psychological “escape” [5]. Domestic psychological studies also consider psychological factors of Internet addiction to be important. Some researchers argue that adolescents’ communicative needs, desire for self-expression, and lack of social support lead to excessive dependence on the Internet [6, 11]. Psychologically, the following conditions have a greater impact on the development of Internet addiction:

1. Feeling of loneliness. In the presence of a lack of social contacts or problems with peers, adolescents may perceive virtual communication as a substitute for real relationships.
2. Anxiety and stress. Adolescents with high levels of anxiety turn to the Internet environment to escape from real-life problems.
3. Depressive states. In individuals with symptoms of depression, the virtual environment appears as a source of temporary psychological relief.
4. Low self-esteem. Lack of self-confidence attracts a teenager to an environment where anonymity and social recognition are easy on the Internet.
5. Emotional instability. Since emotional control is not sufficiently developed during adolescence, the virtual environment can become a powerful motivating factor.

Research discussion. Psychological studies show that Internet addiction is often formed as a result of the interaction of several psychological factors. For example, adolescents with low self-esteem have difficulty communicating with peers and express themselves more freely via the Internet. Another feature of the virtual environment is anonymity. This allows adolescents to show behavioral patterns that they cannot demonstrate in real life. As a result, activities on the Internet create a sense of psychological satisfaction in them. In addition, computer games, social networks and online communication platforms can serve to satisfy the emotional needs of adolescents. However, when this activity becomes excessive, it negatively affects social relationships and educational activities in real life. One of the Uzbek psychological researchers paid special attention to studying the psychological characteristics of adolescents and the Internet environment. His research has extensively analyzed the impact of the Internet environment on the emotional development of a person. According to the researcher, in the conditions of modern “cybernetic society”, young people are constantly in contact with the virtual space, which in some cases can lead to the formation of psychological dependence [7]. In his scientific work, the researcher emphasizes that excessive use of the Internet affects the emotional stability and social adaptation of adolescents. According to him, during adolescence, emotional sensitivity increases, the variety of emotional reactions increases, and the individual actively experiences the process of self-awareness. Therefore, the virtual environment becomes an attractive psychological space for young people [8]. Another group of researchers emphasizes that the virtual environment also affects the process of social identification and self-awareness of the individual. In their opinion, the virtual

identity formed in the Internet environment is inextricably linked to the real social experience of adolescents and, in some cases, can reduce the social activity of an individual in real life [9, 10].

Conclusion. Studies show that the formation of Internet addiction in adolescents often occurs in connection with certain psychological states. In particular, feelings of loneliness, anxiety, depressive mood, low self-esteem and emotional instability increase the risk of excessive Internet use. Therefore, it is important to implement psychological preventive measures to prevent Internet addiction among adolescents. School psychologists and parents need to monitor the psycho-emotional state of adolescents, involve them in real social activities and create a healthy communicative environment. In future studies, it is of great scientific importance to study in more depth the psychological mechanisms of Internet addiction and its impact on personality development.

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